

The Effect of Green Marketing, Brand Awareness, and Attitude on Purchase Intention (Case Study in Consumer Sensatia Botanical)

Putu Panji Aditya Arsana Putra¹
Postgraduate Master's in Management
Mercu Buana University
Jakarta, Indonesia

Daru Asih²
Postgraduate Master's in Management
Mercu Buana University
Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract - This study aims to analyze the effect of green marketing and brand awareness on consumer purchase intention of Sensatia Botanicals which is mediated by attitude. The population of this study are consumers in the age range of 15-56 years, concerned about the environment, users of any brand of skincare, have not known or have never known the Sensatia Botanicals brand with a total sample of 216 valid respondents. The analytical method used in this study is the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with Smart-PLS software. The results of the study found that green marketing had a significant effect on attitudes, as well as brand awareness. Green marketing has a significant effect on purchase intention, as well as brand awareness. Attitudes can mediate green marketing and brand awareness on purchase intention. This study suggests several recommendations for consumers to pay more attention to the skincare products they buy. This research also suggests several recommendations to Sensatia Botanicals to be able to attract more customers to buy its products.

Keywords:- Green Marketing, Brand Awareness, Attitude, Purchase Intention, Skincare.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the issue of Global Warming has become more and more prevalent. Events such as the depletion of the ozone layer which increases the risk of skin cancer, drastic changes in the world's climate due to global warming, and the accumulation of garbage in the sea which results in damage to the ecosystem. A serious problem is the effect of waste, especially plastic waste. Humans as subjects who use all-natural potential in the business world have an important role in shaping an environmentally safe business environment [1]. Terms such as Green Consumerism or the consumerism movement that began with the awareness of humanity to obtain and use products that are safe, decent, and environmentally friendly have finally emerged.

When talking about markets related to "environmentally friendly" products, the market in question is definitely a market with consumable product types such as drinks, food, skin care, makeup, and many more. In this era of globalization coupled with the Covid-19 pandemic, many people have started to consume skin care products to keep

taking care of their skin when they have to stay indoors. As a result, the skincare market remains unchanged and even tends to increase from year to year.

Sensatia Botanicals is a local skincare brand from Karangasem, Bali. According to its official website, Sensatia Botanicals is a local brand that has gone international and is Good Manufacture Practice (GMP) certified and more than 300 of its products have been registered with the Food and Drug Administration (BPOM). This brand has a vision to continue to produce quality products with natural raw materials and without animal testing. Sensatia Botanicals products do not contain and use chemicals or other artificial substances in the production process. In addition, Sensatia Botanicals is also committed to using biodegradable shopping bags and accepting empty bottles for recycling. All bottled products from the brand use recycled bottles, rather than producing new bottles. Sensatia Botanicals sells its products through offline and online stores. Reporting from the official ShopeeMall page, this brand has an official store with 1,423,000 followers and 1,202,000 ratings.

Brands are an essential element of modern life, and have a strong impact on how products and services are perceived and valued [2]. According to AMA (American Marketing Association), a brand is a name, term, sign, symbol, or design or a combination of all of them that is intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers and to distinguish them from those of the competition. There are still not many local Indonesians who know the Sensatia Botanicals brand.

A survey was conducted by ZAP Clinic and Markplus Inc in 2018 regarding skincare product brands that are often used every day where the Sensatia Botanicals brand was completely absent from the survey results chart conducted by ZAP Clinic. The Indonesian government has launched the Bangsa Buatan Indonesia (GBBI) National Movement on May 14, 2020 to promote brands, products made in Indonesia, and also improve the Indonesian economy. It can be concluded that the Sensatia Botanicals brand is still unknown to many Indonesians. Although in fact Sensatia Botanicals is a local brand and domestically produced products originating from Bali. In addition, when viewed from the aspect of green products or green marketing

concepts, Sensatia Botanicals is a brand that has implemented green marketing.

Based on the phenomena and background that have been described and also the results of the pre-survey that has been conducted, the authors are interested in examining the effect of green marketing, brand awareness, and attitudes on consumer buying interest in Sensatia Botanicals.

II. LITERATURE

A. Green Marketing

Green marketing as a concept of product marketing strategies by producers for the needs of consumers who care about the environment. It can also mean the concept of a producer's product marketing strategy that cares about the environment for consumers [3]. Green marketing is the consistency of all activities that design services and facilities for the satisfaction of human needs and desires, with no impact on the natural environment [4]. Green products are products that do not pollute the environment and do not reduce resources or that can be recycled. Green Products, Green Price, Green Place, and Green Promotion are basically the same as the traditional marketing mix. The main difference between these two concepts is that the traditional marketing mix mainly focuses on profit, while on the other hand the green marketing mix focuses on the planet that is necessary for all humans. There are several additional indicators for green marketing such as [5]:

- Environmentally friendly (not harmful to health).
- Resource efficiency (no excess packaging).
- Product price comparison.
- Choosing a price that is proportional to quality.
- Direct marketing.
- Distance of outlets.
- Do not exaggerate attributes or benefits on environmental claims.
- Comparisons with other products should be clear and substantial.

B. Brand Awareness

Brands that are distinctive and easily remembered by consumers are brands that have successfully entered the minds of consumers. In other words, a brand that has succeeded in showing its existence as a product known by consumers [6]. The brand will lead to a sense of habit, especially for products that are low involvement. Habit can lead to liking which can sometimes be a driving force in making purchasing decisions. The common thing to assess brand awareness is a measure of "top of mind" awareness. Brands that are familiar to consumers are an awareness net [7]. It is very clear that it is difficult to sell products whose terms are not known. There are four levels of brand awareness, namely [8]:

- Not aware of brand (unaware of brand).
- Recognizing the brand (brand recognition).
- Brand recall
- Top of mind

C. Attitude

Attitude is an expression of a person's feelings that reflect his liking or dislike for an object [9]. Consumer attitudes are an influential factor in consumer decisions because the concept of attitude is related to the concepts of belief and behavior [10]. Attitude is a psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluating certain objects with some favorable or unfavorable considerations [11]. That attitude is a mental state related to readiness to respond, which is organized through experience and has an impact on directing behavior. There are three indicators of Attitude, namely Cognitive, Affective, and Conative [12].

D. Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is portrayed as a consumer's readiness to purchase a particular product, with pre-known information to reduce risk and increase customer purchase intention. Purchase interest can be identified through indicators of transactional interest, referential interest, preferential interest, and exploratory interest [13]. Purchase interest is the possibility that consumers will make purchases by seeking information from various sources [14]. Purchase interest can be interpreted that a person's desire to buy a product or service is expected to benefit from the product or service purchased [15].

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

From the results of the explanation above, there is a framework of thought used in this study briefly, namely:

Fig 1 : Conceptual Framework

Based on the framework above, there are seven hypotheses in this study, namely:

- H1: Green marketing has a positive effect on attitude.
- H2: Brand awareness has a positive effect on attitude.
- H3: Attitude has a positive effect on purchase intention.
- H4: Green marketing has a positive effect on purchase intention.
- H5: Brand awareness has a positive effect on purchase intention.
- H6: Attitude significantly mediates the relationship between green marketing and purchase intention.
- H7: Attitude significantly mediates the relationship between brand awareness and purchase intention.

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

In this research, the author used quantitative methods. The author sent a link to an online questionnaire through Whatsapp, Instagram, and Facebook. The author used 216 consumer respondents in the age range of Gen Z (15-24 years old), Gen Y (25-40 years old), and Gen X (41-56 years old), concerned about the environment, skincare users of any brand, and have not or never known the Sensatia Botanicals brand for analysis. In the study, the authors used Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with SmartPLS Version 3.2.9 to assess the measurement and structural models.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data on the characteristics of respondents were obtained from questionnaires that had been distributed to 216 respondents who live in Jabodetabek. The findings of this study based on gender are 69.94% female and 33.56% male. Respondents are mostly aged between 15 and 24 years, with a percentage of 49.0%, which in this age range is included in the teenage category. Furthermore, Table 1 contains the results of data analysis that has been processed and the following analysis.

Variables	Items	Outer Loadings	CR	CA	AVE
Green Marketing	GM1	0.773	0.953	0.944	0.692
	GM2	0.837			
	GM3	0.878			
	GM4	0.764			
	GM5	0.903			
	GM6	0.829			
	GM7	0.846			
	GM8	0.819			
	GM9	0.830			
Brand Awareness	BA1	0.729	0.921	0.897	0.661
	BA2	0.820			
	BA4	0.829			
	BA5	0.854			
	BA6	0.852			
	BA7	0.788			
Attitude	A1	0.872	0.944	0.926	0.771
	A2	0.889			
	A3	0.862			
	A4	0.867			
	A5	0.900			
Purchase Intention	PI2	0.919	0.930	0.906	0.727
	PI3	0.844			
	PI4	0.812			
	PI5	0.847			
	PI6	0.838			

Table 1: Reliability Construct and Validity Results

Indicators have good validity and reliability if the outer loading value, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach Alpha value are greater than 0.70. It is also accompanied by an

AVE value greater than 0.5. As shown in Table 1, all outer loading, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach Alpha values from this study exceed 0.7 and the AVE value exceeds 0.5. Based on these results, it can be said that all variables are valid and reliable.

In addition, in this study there is an HTMT test, where this method is used to utilize discriminant validity. It is used for basic measurement using the multitrait-multimethod matrix method. Where it recommends that the measurement value should be smaller than 0.85 although values above 0.85 to a maximum of 0.90 are still considered sufficient. The results below can be stated that all constructs are valid in Discriminant Validity based on HTMT calculations.

Variables	Brand Awareness	Purchase Intention	Green Marketing	Attitude
Brand Awareness				
Purchase Intention	0.802			
Green Marketing	0.776	0.743		
Attitude	0.826	0.804	0.778	

Table 2: HTMT Result

Variables	R-Square	Q-Square
Purchase Intention	0.629	0.452
Attitude	0.653	0.490

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination (R2) and (Q2)

Variables	f-square	Description
Green marketing > Attitude	0.206	Middle
Brand Awareness > Attitude	0.325	Middle
Attitude > Purchase Intention	0.124	Weak
Green Marketing > Purchase Intention	0.049	Weak
Brand Awareness > Purchase Intention	0.084	Weak

Table 4: Coefficient of Determination (F2)

The coefficient of determination R-Square (R2) shows how much the independent variable explains the dependent variable. The R-Square value is zero to one. The R-square value for the purchase intention variable is 0.629, which means that the independent variables can be explained. In addition to the Q-square value, the test shows that the purchase intention value is greater than zero which indicates that the model has fulfilled the relevant predictive value. Meanwhile, the smallest f-square value is shown by the green marketing variable on purchase intention and the strongest is shown by the brand awareness variable on attitude. Furthermore, the results of hypothesis testing of direct effects and indirect effects are in table 5, followed by the results of mediation testing in table 6.

No	Hypothesis	T-Statistics	P Values	Result
H ₁	Green Marketing → Attitude	4.632	0.000	Significant Positive
H ₂	Brand Awareness → Attitude	5.244	0.000	Significant Positive
H ₃	Attitude → Purchase Intention	2.894	0.004	Significant Positive
H ₄	Green Marketing → Purchase Intention	2.003	0.046	Significant Positive
H ₅	Brand Awareness → Purchase Intention	2.681	0.008	Significant Positive
H ₆	Green Marketing → Attitude → Purchase Intention	2.470	0.014	Significant Positive
H ₇	Brand Awareness → Attitude → Purchase Intention	2.562	0.011	Significant Positive

Table 5: Hypothesis Test Results

No	Hypothesis	Confidence Interval 2.5%	Confidence Interval 97.5%	Result
H ₆	Green Marketing → Attitude → Purchase Intention	0.056	0.302	Influential
H ₇	Brand Awareness → Attitude → Purchase Intention	0.054	0.274	Influential

Table 6: Mediation Test Results

Based on the first hypothesis test, there are green marketing results that have a positive and significant effect on attitudes. This shows that the better the green marketing of the Sensatia Bonaticals skincare brand will stimulate a good attitude of potential consumers and the perception that brands or products that develop green marketing are definitely products that are maintained in quality [16].

Based on the second hypothesis test, there are results of brand awareness that have a positive and significant effect on attitudes. It can be interpreted that the better consumers understand the Sensatia Botanicals skincare brand and have an awareness of the importance and use of the Sensatia Botanicals skincare brand will lead to a perception or attitude to better understand the Sensatia Botanicals skincare brand [17].

Furthermore, there are significant positive results from the third hypothesis test, namely attitude towards purchase intention. The attitude of potential consumers towards the Sensatia Bonaticals skincare brand will arise if there is a tendency to have an interest in purchasing, if potential

consumers have a good attitude such as seeking information about the Sensatia Botanicals skincare brand, looking for alternative choices for purchasing skincare brands, it is certain that potential consumers already have an interest in buying Sensatia Botanicals skincare brand products [18].

There are positive and significant results in the fourth hypothesis test, namely green marketing on purchase intention. The better the impact of green products on the Sensatia Botanicals skincare brand, the higher the level of buying interest of potential customers of the Sensatia Botanicals skincare brand. Prospective consumers will not hesitate to buy if a product has been proven and confirmed to be environmentally friendly [19].

Based on the fifth hypothesis test, there are positive and significant results of brand awareness on purchase intention. This reflects that the brand awareness of potential consumers of the Sensatia Botanicals skincare brand can influence an interest in purchasing Sensatia Botanicals skincare products, due to the extent to which potential customers know Senastia Botanicals skincare products, the more potential customers recognize the product, the higher the purchase interest of potential customers in the Senastia Botanicals skincare brand [20].

There are positive and significant results from the sixth hypothesis test, namely green marketing on purchase intention mediated by attitude. Attitude mediation between green marketing and purchase intention means that the importance of green marketing and one's attitude affects interest which will ultimately determine whether consumers will behave or not after feeling an awareness of the aspects of green and environmentally friendly marketing. The attitude mediation variable falls into the type of partial mediation because the attitude variable is able to influence green marketing on purchase intention, although the existence of the attitude variable does not really affect the presence or absence of being a mediating variable [21].

Furthermore, there are positive and significant results from the seventh hypothesis test, namely brand awareness on purchase intention mediated by attitude. In general, the right attitude chosen by consumers can bridge the importance of brand awareness for potential consumers to make a purchase or not. The attitude mediation variable is included in the type of partial mediation because the attitude variable is able to influence brand awareness on purchase intention, although the attitude variable does not really affect the presence or absence of being a mediating variable [22].

VI. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on the research results, the authors provide several suggestions to the management of Sensatia Botanicals as follows:

- Convince potential customers that products that implement green or environmentally friendly marketing are in accordance with standards and are kept safe so that potential customers do not hesitate to buy products.

- The high interest of potential consumers in green or environmentally friendly products, for Sensatia Botanicals skincare to maintain the quality of the ingredients and ingredients contained in their products so that potential customers feel confident and safe when buying or when using their products.
- Based on the results of the f-square analysis, the highest lift is obtained, namely 0.325 (Medium) with the category of brand awareness variables on the attitude of potential consumers. It can be concluded that Sensatia Botanicals should prioritize promoting its products widely and developing a wide range of environmentally friendly green products because potential customers of Sensatia Botanicals have sufficient awareness of brands and skincare products that implement green products.
- Based on the results of the mediation effect, namely Partial Mediation, it can be explained that the presence or absence of consumer attitudes does not affect buying interest in green products such as Sensatia Botanicals Skincare because green marketing and brand awareness are sufficient to directly influence consumer buying interest in using green products. To the owner of Sensatia Botanicals skincare to focus more on promoting green products to consumers widely and thoroughly through platforms or social media such as Instagram, Facebook, Tiktok and others so that consumers have an awareness of the importance of protecting the environment and using green products so that they have an interest in every purchase of Sensatia Botanicals Skincare products.

VII. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The results showed that green marketing, brand awareness, and attitude have a significant positive relationship with Sensatia Botanicals purchase intention. Attitude variables can mediate between green marketing and purchase intention with partial mediation type. In the end, the attitude of potential consumers who tend to choose environmentally friendly products and Sensatia Botanicals skincare products can bridge the awareness of a consumer to purchase Sensatia Botanicals skincare products or not.

Future research which interested in researching purchase intention and attitudes related to green marketing and brand awareness can retest the variables in this study but by adding or changing some of the variables studied such as (Religiosity, Quality, Promotion, Trust, Motivation and Word of Mouth).

Increasing the number of research objects can also increase the number of research respondents so that they become more generalized and represent green products or environmentally friendly products. Future researchers are expected to add other variables not examined by researchers that influence attitudes and interests in purchasing green products.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Soelton, M., Rohman, F., Asih, D., Saratian, E. T., & Wiguna, S. B. "Green Marketing That Effect the Buying Intention Healthcare Products". *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 12, No. 15, 2022
- [2]. Gao, Y. "Brand Awareness, Purchase Intention And Price Premium Of International Airlines Operating Between Australia and The United Kingdom". *Published by Scholarly Commons*, Volume 6, Issue 3, 2019
- [3]. Manongko, A. A. "Green Marketing (Suatu Perspektif Marketing Mix & Theory of Planned Behavior)". *Minahasa: Yayasan Wakaria Waya*, 2018
- [4]. Ottman, J. A. "The New Rules Of Green Marketing". *London: Greenleaf Publishing Limited*, 2011
- [5]. Hayat, K., Nadeem, A., & Jan, S. "The Impact Of Green Marketing Mix On Green Buying Behavior: (A Case Of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Evidence From The Customers)". *City University Research Journal*, 27 – 40, 2019
- [6]. Alamsyah, D. P., & Febriani, R. "Green Customer Behaviour: Impact Of Green Brand Awareness To Green Trust". *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2019
- [7]. Aaker, D. A., & McLoughlin, D. "Strategic Market Management: Global Perspectives". *John Wiley & Sons*, 2010
- [8]. Tyas, N. S. "Pengaruh Brand Credibility, Word Of Mouth dan Emotional Value Terhadap Attitude Serta Implikasinya Pada Purchase Intention Telemedicine Halodoc". *Thesis Mercubuana University*, 2021
- [9]. Firmansyah, M. A. "Perilaku Konsumen". *Yogyakarta: Deepublish*, 2018
- [10]. Eagly, A. H., & Chaiken, S. "Attitude Strength, Attitude Structure, And Resistance To Change". *Hillsdale: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc*, 1995
- [11]. Sangadji, & Sopiah. "Perilaku Konsumen : Pendekatan Praktis Disertai Himpunan Jurnal Penelitian". *Edisi pertama. Yogyakarta: Andi*, 2013
- [12]. Siyal, S., Ahmed, M., Ahmad, R., Khan, B., & Xin, C. "Factors Influencing Green Purchase Intention: Moderating Role of Green Brand Knowledge". *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 22 pages, 2021
- [13]. Handhayani, I., & Mulia, D. "What Drives Smartphone Purchase Intention? Perspective from Technology, Price, and E-Wom as Mediators". *International Journal of Innovation Science and Research Technology*, 1(8), 2023
- [14]. Shahnaz, N. B. F., & Wahyono. "Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Minat Beli Konsumen Di Toko Online". *Management Analysis Journal*, 389 – 399, 2016
- [15]. Siyal, S., Ahmed, M., Ahmad, R., Khan, B., & Xin, C. "Factors Influencing Green Purchase Intention: Moderating Role of Green Brand Knowledge". *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 22 pages, 2021
- [16]. Baiquni, A. M., & Ishak, A. "The Green Purchase Intention Of Tupperware Products: The Role Of Green Brand Positioning". *Jurnal Siasat Bisnis*, 1-14, 2019

- [17]. Jung, N. Y., & Seock, Y.-K. “The Impact of Corporate Reputation on Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention”. *Fashion and Textiles*, 15 pages, 2016
- [18]. Kaur, B., Gangwar, V. P., & Dash, G. “Green Marketing Strategies, Environmental Attitude, and Green Buying Intention: A Multi-Group Analysis in an Emerging Economy Context. *Sustainability*”, 16 pages, 2022
- [19]. Agustin, R. D., Kumadji, S., & Yulianto, E. “Pengaruh Green Marketing Terhadap Minat Beli Serta Dampaknya Pada Keputusan Pembelian (Survei Pada Konsumen Non-Member Tupperware Di Kota Malang)”. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)*, Vol. 22 No. 2, 2015
- [20]. Eliasari, P. A., & Sukaatmadja, I. P. “Pengaruh Brand Awareness Terhadap Purchase Intention Dimediasi Oleh Perceived Quality Dan Brand Loyalty”. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud*, 6620-6650, 2017
- [21]. Khoiriyah, S., & Toro, M. J. “Attitude Toward Green Product, Willingness To Pay And Intention To Purchase”. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 620-628, 2018
- [22]. Permana, D. “Recognizing the Islamic Banking Consumer Behaviour from the Perspective of Product Knowledge, Brand Awareness and Attitude”. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 16 – 22, 2019